

A FEASIBILITY STUDY ON CHOOSING A STORE LOCATION FOR A COFFEE SHOP

1. Mr. S.Saravanan.,AP/MBA, Sona college of Technology, salem.
Dr. M.S. Kamalaveni., AP/MBA, Sona college of Technology, salem.
2. Mrs. G. Madhumadhi MBA., M.phil (Ph. D).,
AP/BBA, Sona college of Arts&Science, salem.
3. Mrs. Sai Sangeetha., salem

ABSTRACT

The success of a business lies in how well the business can reach its customers. Choosing the right place is as important as any other factor. Finding the best location for a coffee shop can quickly become frustrating due to limited availability, high rent prices, and lousy landlords. To find the right business location, researchers need to think beyond rent prices and physical space. It helps in creating a good brand image and reputation. Selecting a location in the vicinity of a business district, shopping mall, or a university is always a good option. This study aims to find a suitable location for one such coffee shop in Salem city. Data is collected through a questionnaire with a sample size of 175. Various analyses such as factor-wise data analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, etc. are carried out to meet the objectives of the study and it includes the Garret ranking method to identify the preference of the consumers. The study would help choose a store location for a coffee shop in the selected study area to increase the number of customers, acquire brand reputation/image, increase sales and thereby the profit and customers can access the shop in their locality.

Keywords: beverage store location, retail store site selection, store selection factors, location congruence etc.,

INTRODUCTION

Across the world, Coffee and tea are the most popular beverages consumed by everyone. It is a fact that coffee has been consumed since 800 AD. Brazil is the country with the most coffee production and growth. The success of coffee as a beverage owes to both the caffeine as well as the sensory pleasure it gives. Coffee consumption is increasing day by day and therefore it is essential to source more goods, local coffee, and bakery items. While at home, the consumption of coffee and tea with the preferred tastes meet all their desires, but the available options are limited at the workplace and in other places. This need was understood by the companies and it led to the idea of expanding the service to several locations. So why is the coffee shop so important? As the researcher enters a coffee shop, it is hard to ignore the cool and cozy atmosphere, the pleasant music in the background, the time researcher spends with our friends and loved ones, etc. How wonderful it will be to have coffee at a coffee bar like this? It is a place where researchers could share lots of emotions with a sip of coffee in a relaxing atmosphere. Along with the growth of coffee consumption, so did the number of coffee shops. The demand increased with the passage of time and coffee shop owners wanted

to bring up new technologies to fulfill the demands. That is when they came up with the solution of automated coffee vending machines which was first invented in 1947 in The United States. During the early stages, coffee dispensers came only with a single option. Later two, three, and four options were developed over time. Most of the coffee shops that are active at present almost offer the same variety and menu. The question is how new start-up coffee shops manage to pull the crowd. This is not an easy task in this competitive world where there are several leading coffee shops. There arise several questions in such cases. What makes them unique? How well they provide service? How is the quality, pricing? etc. A unique selling point makes the coffee shop to stand out in the competitive market. A unique selling point not only means the price and quality. It includes something which can attract the target market which your friends or relatives talk about to others. It must be something that can't be easily copied by any other. Well, it is of course not so easy and lots of effort needs to be put in. A factor which acts as a major determinant is the location selection of coffee shops. If the owner of a coffee shop wants more customers, it is essential to expand the coffee shop to various locations where there are more footfalls. The surrounding matters a lot- the landmarks and other shops around also plays a major role in the business. Out of several locations, the best one must be chosen concerning the cost as well as the above factors. This study aims to find a suitable location for one such new coffee shop, this is been a start-up coffee business in the Tamilnadu region, namely in the city of Salem.

Fig 1: Outline of the framework

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Location analysis of a shop:

The concept of automation was explained by **E Bellis and G V Johar (2020)** in their research. This research focuses on one such technology called as the autonomous shopping system to which consumers delegate shopping decisions and tasks. Research on the financial feasibility of the AHS GAN shop was carried out by **Francisca Hermawan (2019)** with primary and secondary data and projected data for the next five years. The Net Present Value and Pay Back Period were used to measure the financial feasibility; this analysis showed that the owner needs to adapt the plan and strategies as external conditions influencing the business keeps changing. Another article by **M Guillen-Royo (2019)** explores the relationship between sustainable consumption and wellbeing and the role of online shopping. The results show that online shopping increases life satisfaction by lowering the cost of engaging in sustainable consumption practices. The same is applicable for food consumption also. The research by **R Sujarit and P Sirikamonsin (2019)** focused on a similar product like the coffee. The study's objective was to find ways to expand a furniture shop. Choosing a location is one that suits the business due to the availability of resources and convenient transportation. Maintaining a good customer relationship after sales were one of the best ways to create an impression among customers. **Linder G Ringo (2009)** carried out research that conveyed the importance of selecting a profitable location for a business. The research details the necessary steps for conducting site selection analysis using Geographical Indication System (GIS) to determine potential areas for the establishment of a coffee house franchise. The finding was that successful client market area identification and segmentation have a positive impact on business growth.

Coffee Shop Strategies:

In a study conducted by **Abi Adeleke (2019)**, the various marketing methods of the coffee shop were analyzed. The concept of Goldsmith's 8Ps of the marketing mix was used in this study. Data was collected through interviews, websites, and public reviews. These were analyzed using the content analysis method. It was observed that owners of successful coffee shops were actively engaged in the community, which included social media for marketing and business operations. Such marketing strategies lead to new job creation and also economic sustainability. **G Pardalis et. al., (2018)** observed the views of construction SMEs in Sweden. Interviews were conducted with 10 SMEs and a conceptual framework was applied lack of interest is mostly related to perceived complexity. Complexity is seen as a preventing factor that puts the business at stake. The study conducted by **T Sumarti and S F Falatehan (2016)** aimed to increase the young coffee farmers' interest to become entrepreneurs. A sample of young farmers aged between 20 and 40 was taken. The research showed that already there was equality in access and control carried out by young coffee farmers and their parents. A gap seems to happen as there are several female young coffee farmers as well as females mothers that do not have control or benefits over resources. **B Chiputwa et. al., (2015)** in their research analyzed the impacts of sustainability standards on the lives of small coffee farmers in Uganda. Using survey data and propensity score matching with multiple treatments it was found that fair-trade certification increases household living

standards and reduces prevalence and depth of poverty. Similarly in a research carried out by **Sadeeq G, et. al., (2015)**, it was found that a coffee shop should achieve a sustainable competitive advantage through the manipulation of the elements of marketing mix comprising the 7Ps elements. The product must stand different from others through a distinctive competitive advantage which creates a unique selling point. The study mainly focuses on various strategies that must be implemented for a successful business and also focus on the goals of the organization more efficiently and effectively. **S Patel and L Farrel (2013)** studied the importance of Open Education along and Coffee houses in Europe at the beginning of the industrial revolution. Coffee houses were seen as an unprecedented moment of openness, later which became a failure. Thus, coffee houses remind us of the extent to which free and untrammelled education can quickly become non-institutionalized. According to **Leoncio F. Barlan Jr. (2013)**, the personnel requirements for a coffee shop includes college or associate graduates. Skilled labor was not required as employees will be trained before entering the operations. Employees encountered inadequate payroll problems followed by duplication of duties during the operation. The analysis of the coffee shop market in the UK was carried out by **Wen-Ko Liang (2011)**. The coffee market in the UK is very competitive through various manners, such as service, quality of coffee, price of products, the atmosphere of a coffee shop, etc. Apart from this the external environment also has little effect on the coffee market. In **(2006) Wen-Hwa Ko and Chihwei** focused on the selection of an optimal alternative for the planning of a new coffee shop based on customer satisfaction. They used a modified Delphi method involving 5 experts and 10 coffee shop managers. Data were analyzed using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). The study showed that coffee shop in a commercial area was most preferable, followed by a school or hospital center. This method was found to be a good method for decision-making.

Consumer behavior:

Another research conducted by **R Takahashi et. al., (2018)** focused on investigating the consumer purchasing behavior for certified forest coffee affected by consumer interest in environmental issues. A combination of Randomized Control Trial (RCT) and eye-tracking techniques were used to study the purchasing behavior. It was found that the concern towards environmental issues doesn't significantly affect consumers' purchasing behavior. According to research by **Do Tu and Linh (2017)**, the market situation, customer perspicacity of Vietnamese coffee, and estimated finance for business, scopes, and limitations were analyzed. The research by **M Nadanyiova (2015)** studied the level of knowledge and satisfaction of Slovak consumers. It was found that consumers considered the quality as an important impact on their final purchasing decision. In a study conducted by **A Susanty and E Kenny (2015)**, the effect of brand equity on customer satisfaction and brand loyalty of Starbucks and Excelso coffee shop were investigated. Data was collected through questionnaires. The results showed that the physical quality, the ideal Self-congruence, and lifestyle congruence have a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction in Excelso; whereas it was only brand identification in the case of Starbucks. However, customer satisfaction was common in both shops. The research by **H Vanharanta et. al., (2015)** examined the formation and measuring of customer experience in services. The results and feedback gathered were used to verify and validate the usability and structure of ontology

and application created. The application operated well. It was noted that customers seemed to be searching for ways to get more value out of the company's service. The study by **N B Carvalho (2015)** aimed to validate and predict, by discriminant analysis technique, the coffee consumer group obtained by cluster analysis. The analysis showed significant potential to predict the behavior of individuals. The consumer group can be characterized based on profile and behavior and create reliable strategies to meet the needs of target consumer segments. Research conducted by **Junio Andreti, et. al., (2013)** aimed at identifying the increase in coffee shops day by day through analysis of various factors such as product, price, place, promotion, etc. A sample of 300 was taken to collect the required data. The F test and ANOVA were used to extend factors influential to customer buying decisions. It was observed that customer footfalls are based on price, promotion, and service quality provided. Another research by **Li-Mei Hung (2012)** focused on the benefits of a budget coffee shop, consumer characteristics, buying behavior, and cost-effectiveness. Data were collected with a sample of 480 consumers in Taichung through closed questionnaire and linear relationships for basic individual information and consumer behavior using SPSS. The study showed that consumers with steady jobs and income possess higher consumer characteristics than those who don't have steady jobs and income.

Coffee shop location:

B Rahardjo et, al., (2019) analyzed the internal and external factors that affect the coffee business and to formulate strategies. A combination of Business Model Canvas (BMC) and SWOT matrix analysis was used. The result showed that the optimization of various resources leads to an increase in key activities, partners, channels, segments, etc. A financial analysis was carried out by **Menghao Wang (2019)** of Luckin coffee. It stated the operating ability, profitability, and development ability of the shop. It was found that the advantages and disadvantages can lead to typical attributes such as corporate profitability, high-risk debt, etc. The findings were that for good operating conditions, good sales need to be maintained and scale of market development and the R&D investment needs to be controlled. The research by **Lauren Porter (2018)** aimed to frame a business plan for a coffee project in downtown Bartlesville. This involved the study of the target market, the population in that region, the source of coffee beans, the fund of business, etc. Research by **Alec N et. al., (2017)** intends to present the profile of coffee shops in terms of years in the business, location, type of ownership, etc. The impact of tourism on coffee shops was also studied. A descriptive method of research was used. Results showed that the majority of coffee shops are in Lipa city. There is no significant difference in the impacts of coffee shop business on the tourism industry when grouped according to profile variable. In the research conducted by **A Mishra and R Vishvas (2016)** the store strategy was studied using retail shopper empowerment scores. Using the empowerment metric, retailers can understand consumer preferences regarding store experience. It was understood that it is possible to improve customer experience and the financial performance of the store by modifying the retail shopper empowerment framework. The analysis of impacts of labor costs, rent, and availability of skilled labor, store location, population density, and the competition was carried out by **Hemalatha and Sridevi (2008)**. The primary objective was to adopt a DSS framework to evaluate critical factors that contribute to successful managerial decisions.

According to the research carried out by **Linda Qin (2004)**, Best Coffee Canada, a well-known coffee company has its Franchise in China named Best Coffee China (CCC). However, they are lacking a centralized decision-making team. This research aimed to examine the key success factors for Best Coffee to thrive in China and provide reasons that hinder their growth using Porter's five forces to analyze external and internal factors.

RESEARCH GAP

Many researches have been focused on improving the sales through various strategies but this study primarily focus on how the location plays a major role in the business. In this research, researchers are going to select a location for a coffee shop in the city of Salem, Tamilnadu-India. The research is carried out in different stages by analysing the household income and coffee consumption pattern of the customer through a questionnaire. Second, the customer footfalls in selected areas of the city are observed and financially the most efficient location is selected by analysing the investment. Both the primary and secondary data are used in this analysis.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study devoted to the following objectives:

- To identify an appropriate location for a coffee shop in the Salem region.
- To find out various factors influencing the on-site selection of coffee shop
- To analyze the preferences of the respondents towards selecting an appropriate location identified in the Salem region.
- To provide suggestions for store location and store selection parameters.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design used in the study is a descriptive research and this research largely uses methods such as questionnaires and surveys with set questions and answers that respondents tick from a predefined selection and also interviewed the experienced person as an opinion leader. The primary and secondary data were used. The primary data collected were analyzed by using statistical tools like descriptive statistics, factor wise analysis, correlation, regression, garret ranking, and ANOVA. Before the responses were collected, a pilot study was conducted among the 30 Customers of the coffee shop.

Sample Design:

The sample size consists of 200 respondents from diverse combinations of age groups, occupations, and education so that the sample is not biased. The sample size of our research is limited to 200 people only. Out of 200 people, only 175 responses were valid. The study was carried out for one and a half months, from 1st April to 15th May 2022.

ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

Percentage Analysis

Totally 200 responses were collected out of which 175 Responses are considered for this research.

Table 1: Classification of people

Age	No. of people	Percentage
15-25 years	92	52.6
26-40 years	39	22.3
41-55 years	23	13.1
56 years & above	21	12.0
Total	175	100.0
Gender	No. of people	Percentage
Male	97	55.4
Female	78	44.6
Total	175	100.0
Annual household income	No. of people	Percentage
Below 3 lakhs	48	27.4
3-5 lakhs	52	29.7
5-10 lakhs	49	28.0
10 lakhs & more	26	14.9
Total	175	100.0
Education	No. of people	Percentage
Schooling	8	4.6
High School	10	5.7
Graduation	88	50.3
Post-Graduation	64	36.6
Others	5	2.9
Total	175	100.0
Occupation	No. of people	Percentage
Student	57	32.6
Service(govt)	17	9.7
Business	41	23.4
Professional	43	24.6
Other	17	9.7
Total	175	100.0
Locality	No. of people	Percentage
Urban	126	72.0
Rural	29	16.6
Semi-urban	20	11.4
Total	175	100.0

The above table shows data on the number of people who are consumers of coffee of different age groups belonging to different households with varying income as shown above. It is seen that people in the urban region are major consumers of coffee.

Based on the above chart, most of them prefer hot beverages to cold ones. This is a positive note for this research as coffee is a hot beverage.

The above chart that the numbers of coffee consumers are more compared to any other beverage. This acts as an added advantage in this research.

The majority of people consume coffee at home. Next to this are coffee bars and cafeteria which are most preferred by the consumers.

The above chart show the preferred days on which people visit a coffee shop. The majority of them don't have a particular day to visit coffee bars and are mostly dependent on their time constraints. For the majority of them, the preferred time is evening.

The above figure shows that the Kaapi stop is equally popular with that of Café Coffee Day in the Salem region. It is to be noted here that both the coffee shops are branded and Kaapi Stop is a new venture in Salem.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Based on the review of the literature, there are five factors that influence the selection of an appropriate location for a coffee shop and the customer perception of the shop is also determined. The five factors are Product, Price, Promotion, Place, and service quality.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Factors	Statements	Mean	SD
Product	Product serving is found satisfied	4.2343	0.8489
	The diverse selection of coffee beverages	4.0171	0.7229
	Quality of coffee	3.9771	0.7501
	Appealing aroma	4.0286	0.7613
	Unique flavor/taste	4.1200	0.8921
Price	Reasonable Price	4.2857	0.7794
	Value for money	4.0229	0.7727
Promotion	Media advertisement	4.2057	0.8185
	Seasonal Offer	3.9829	0.7985
Place	Clean & bright store interior	4.3486	0.7101
	Ambiance/hygiene of store	4.2114	0.6573
	The comfort of café(Convenience)	4.2914	0.7510
	Toilet	4.3086	0.7999
Service quality	Staff Friendliness	4.3371	0.7075
	Supply of freely available sugar packets, paper towel	4.2171	0.6770
	Staff service speed	4.0971	0.7781
	Information regarding notice of delay in delivery	4.0800	0.9124
	Providing timely & prompt service	4.1257	0.7627

The averages of all variables are equal and almost nearer to 4.230, which shows that the responses are normally distributed and the perceived level of the responses was satisfactory. The Standard deviation of the variables is equal and almost nearer to 0.77, which also shows that the responses are normally distributed and the level of responses was good.

RELIABILITY TEST

A reliability test refers to the degree to which a test is consistent and stable in measuring what it is intended to measure. Most simply put, a test is reliable if it is consistent within itself and across time.

Table 3: Reliability Coefficient

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
0.908	18

The collected data taken was found to be better reliability with a coefficient (Cronbach alpha) of about 0.908 which infers that highly reliable (with 1 being the maximum reliability) in nature. The reliability test in this research is carried out by using the Likert

scale (through a survey questionnaire). Since the responses were consistent and balanced, the reliability coefficient is high.

FACTOR WISE DATA ANALYSIS

To know the distribution of the replies of various respondents, descriptive statistics have been used.

Table 4: Factor wise data analysis

	Product	Price	Promotion	Place	Service quality
N Valid	175	175	175	175	175
Mean	4.0754	4.1543	4.0943	4.2900	4.1714
Std. Deviation	0.5843	0.6795	0.7079	0.5419	0.5684
Skewness	-0.784	-0.631	-0.486	-1.010	-0.662

The mean of all three factors is equal and nearly close to 4.7, which shows that the responses are normally distributed and at a satisfactory level. The Standard deviation of the promotion factor (0.7079) is high when compared to other factors which signifies that the understanding of the responses has deviated for the promotion factor followed them.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Five factors influence the selection of an appropriate location for a coffee shop and the customer perception of the coffee shop. The location fixing and customer perception in a shop are examined for the degree of relationship among these five factors to determine how the fluctuation of one factor affects the other and also to identify similar, factors are measured for Bi-variate correlation concerning each other and their coefficients are specified in the following table:

Table 5: Correlation Analysis

	Product	Price	Promotion	Place	Service quality
Product	1	0.632**	0.451**	0.498**	0.575**
Price		1	0.459**	0.514**	0.558**
Promotion			1	0.430**	0.487**
Place				1	0.666**
Service quality					1

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

From the above table, it shows that there is a high correlation (0.666) between the place and service quality. Hence, place alone doesn't determine the business. The quality of the product also plays a major role.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

To know the effect of the various factors on customer perception in the coffee shop, regression analysis was performed keeping the overall product, price, promotion, place, and service quality as the independent variable and overall satisfaction as a dependent variable.

Table 6: Regression Analysis

S.no	Factors	Regression Coefficient
1	Product	0.241
2	Price	0.280
3	Promotion	0.292
4	Place	0.224
5	Service quality	0.234
	R²	1.000
	F Statistics	0.000
	Significance	0.000

As R^2 is greater than 0.5, henceforth there is an impact of the five factors on customer perception. The factors such as product (0.241), price (0.280), promotion (0.292), place (0.224) and service quality (0.234) have a significant impact on the perception.

ONE-WAY ANOVA

Keeping this as an objective, the data was collected and worked out for the testing of the hypothesis at a 5% level of significance using the Analysis of Variance.

a) Association between Product and Demographic profile of Respondent

To know the association between the product and the Demographic profile of the Respondent, one-way ANOVA is used by keeping the product as the dependent and the demographic profile of responses as the factor, and the analysis is done.

H_0 : There is no association between the product and the Demographic profile of the Respondent

H_1 : There is an association between the product and Demographic profile of Respondent

Table 7: Association between Product and Demographic profile of Respondent

Factors	Demographic profile	F value	Significance	Result
Product	Age	1.877	0.041	Ho is Rejected
Product	Gender	1.535	0.116	Ho is Accepted
Product	Annual Income	1.854	0.044	Ho is Rejected
Product	Education	2.247	0.012	Ho is Rejected
Product	Occupation	0.992	0.459	Ho is Accepted
Product	Locality	1.192	0.293	Ho is Accepted

H_0 is Accepted, which suggests there is no significant difference between product (factor of customer perception) and Gender, occupation, and locality (Demographic profile of visitors).

b) Association between Price and Demographic profile of Respondent

To know the association between the Price and Demographic profile of Respondent, one way ANOVA is used by keeping the price as the dependent and demographic profile of responses as the factor and the analysis is done.

H_0 : There is no Association between price and Demographic profile of Respondent

H_1 : There is an association between price and Demographic profile of Respondent

Table 8: Association between price and Demographic profile of Respondent

Factors	Demographic profile	F value	Significance	Result
Price	Age	1.625	0.143	Ho is Accepted
Price	Gender	1.418	0.210	Ho is Accepted
Price	Annual Income	2.932	0.010	Ho is Rejected
Price	Education	0.517	0.795	Ho is Accepted
Price	Occupation	0.884	0.508	Ho is Accepted
Price	Locality	3.703	0.002	Ho is Rejected

H_0 is Accepted, which suggests there is no significant difference between price (factor of customer perception), and age, gender, education, and occupation (Demographic profile of visitors).

c) Association between Promotion and Demographic profile of Respondent

To know the association between promotion and Demographic profile of Respondent, one way ANOVA is used by keeping promotion as the dependent and demographic profile of responses as the factor and the analysis is carried out.

H_0 : There is no Association between promotion and Demographic profile of Respondent

H_1 : There is an Association between promotion and Demographic profile of Respondent

Table 8: Association between promotion and Demographic profile of Respondent

Factors	Demographic profile	F value	Significance	Result
Promotion	Age	1.784	0.105	Ho is Accepted
Promotion	Gender	1.365	0.231	Ho is Accepted
Promotion	Annual Income	3.770	0.002	Ho is Rejected
Promotion	Education	0.705	0.646	Ho is Accepted
Promotion	Occupation	1.421	0.209	Ho is Accepted
Promotion	Locality	1.310	0.255	Ho is Accepted

H_0 is Accepted, which suggests there is no significant difference between promotion (factor of customer perception), and age, gender, education, occupation, and locality (Demographic profile of visitors).

d) Association between place and Demographic profile of Respondent

To know the association between the place and Demographic profile of Respondent, one way ANOVA is used by keeping the place as the dependent and demographic profile of responses as the factor and the analysis is done.

H_0 : There is no Association between place and Demographic profile of Respondent

H_1 : There is an association between place and Demographic profile of Respondent

Table 9: Association between place and Demographic profile of Respondent

Factors	Demographic profile	F value	Significance	Result
Place	Age	1.109	0.359	Ho is Accepted
Place	Gender	1.028	0.420	Ho is Accepted
Place	Annual Income	0.815	0.603	Ho is Accepted
Place	Education	1.818	0.068	Ho is Accepted
Place	Occupation	1.382	0.200	Ho is Accepted
Place	Locality	0.325	0.966	Ho is Accepted

H_0 is Accepted, which suggests there is no significant difference between place (factor of customer perception), and age, Gender, Annual income, Education, occupation, and locality (Demographic profile of visitors).

e) Association between service quality and Demographic profile of Respondent

To know the association between the service quality and Demographic profile of Respondent, one way ANOVA is been used by keeping the service quality as the dependent and demographic profile of responses as the factor and the analysis is done.

H_0 : There is no Association between service quality and Demographic profile of Respondent

H_1 : There is an association between service quality and Demographic profile of Respondent

Table 10: Association between service quality and Demographic profile of Respondent

Factors	Demographic profile	F value	Significance	Result
Service quality	Age	1.779	0.061	Ho is Rejected
Service quality	Gender	0.675	0.760	Ho is Accepted
Service quality	Annual Income	2.204	0.016	Ho is Rejected
Service quality	Education	1.599	0.103	Ho is Accepted
Service quality	Occupation	1.500	0.136	Ho is Accepted
Service quality	Locality	2.013	0.030	Ho is Rejected

H_0 is Accepted, which suggests there is no significant difference between service quality (factor of customer perception), and Gender, education, and occupation (Demographic profile of visitors).

GARRET RANKING

To find out the most significant factor which influences the respondent, Garrett's ranking technique is used. As per this method, respondents are asked to assign the rank for all factors, and the outcomes of such ranking are converted into score value.

Table 11: Calculation of Ranking

S. no	Locality	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Total	%	Rank
1	Old bus Stand	1326	1320	1798	2400	1376	665	176	9061	14.73	3
2	Junction (Railway station)	1872	1386	2494	2150	559	665	264	9390	15.27	2
3	Seelanaickenpatti	2652	2970	2030	600	1075	560	176	9887	16.08	1
4	Kondalampatti	1482	1518	1160	1750	1161	840	594	8505	13.83	6
5	New bus stand	2184	1254	1218	1000	1720	1225	264	8865	14.41	5
6	Vinayaga Mission (1008 sivan temple)	780	924	522	800	1032	1540	1276	6874	11.18	7
7	4 Roads	3432	2112	986	50	602	665	1056	8903	14.48	4

The ranking for various locations is found out. The top three location preferences are Seelanaickenpatti, Junction respectively. The other areas for the location preference are followed as per the above table.

FINDINGS

The location analysis of coffee shop has resulted in the following findings:

- The data collected is from those people who are restricted to that particular city (Salem) alone with around 175 responses. About 52.6% of the responses are from younger people aged between 15 and 25.
- 55.4% of the respondents are males while the rest are females.
- More than 50% of the respondents are graduated and the majority of them are either students or professionals.
- The respondents are the maximum in the urban region with 72% of the response for the survey.
- Coffee consumption depends upon several factors such as age, an income of a household, place of residence (urban or rural), place of study/work, etc.
- Hot beverages are mostly preferred by consumers (64.6% prefer hot beverages, whereas 35.4% prefer cold beverages).
- About 55% of them prefer coffee to any other hot beverages according to the survey.
- People in the urban region consume more coffee than in the rural region. Urban people are more attracted to coffee consumption.
- Home and College/office cafeteria is the most preferred place to have coffee which constitutes 29.1%, 24%, and 24% respectively.
- Coffee is consumed by the people regularly, i.e., either every day or during weekends. Most people drink coffee based on their time constraints or as and when required.

- About 74% of the coffee consumers prefer evening time for coffee.
- There are five factors which influence the selection of appropriate location for a coffee shop- Product, Price, Place, Promotion, and service quality.
- The descriptive analysis of these five factors shows that the data is normally distributed and the responses are satisfactory.
- According to the reliability test, the Cronbach's alpha was made use and the value resulted showed that the collected data is highly reliable.
- The standard deviation of the promotion factor is alone high which shows that there is a deviation in understanding the promotion factor by the respondents.
- Correlation analysis was carried out between the five factors. It resulted in that place and service quality are highly correlated.
- Regression analysis shows that product, price, promotion, and place influence consumer perception.
- The ANOVA tests show that there is no association of product, price, promotion, place, and service quality with that of the demographic profile.
- According to the Garret Ranking method, Seelanaickanpatti is the most preferred location by consumers with a preference of 16.08%. Vinayaga Mission area is the least preferred location with 11.18%.
- The reason for expansion is to provide more employment opportunities, entering new markets, and introduce market share, delivery of products, and services to a wider area.

SUGGESTIONS

The location of a coffee shop must be selected in such a way that there are landmarks where the customer footfall is high.

- A coffee shop can also be started in developing areas. This leads to the coffee shop being the first landmark in that area.
- According to FSSAI food standards to be complied with and this will build the image among customers.
- Store parameters like ample space for car parking, Good ambiance, More floating, Local people accessible, Visibility of shop, Safety/ crime rate, Health regulation (hygienic area), Proximity to suppliers, Future growth, and creating the landmark, Competition, Demographics, and Labor availability also influence in the selection of store location.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis, the researchers conclude that the coffee shop industry is a very attractive market (high margins, growing demand) for the companies that are already established and those that will come up in the future. The growth of the coffee shop acts as an opportunity for employment, delivery of service to different areas, etc. The location analysis process is a major step in the business as it increases the number of customers (footfalls), helps the coffee shop acquire a brand image, serves as a way to increase the profits, and even

more. Several actions are recommended for the business. First, the enterprise has to maintain high customer traffic in its store to sustain all sales targets. This would include studies on maximizing store hours and including weekends in-store operations. Second, ensuring sustainability will require a periodic evaluation of strategies used on all aspects of the venture and adjusting the strategies to fit the needs and wants of customers. Extensive promotion of products is recommended.

Some of the benefits if the shop is located according to the place which the researcher chooses based on the analysis are an Increased number of customers, acquire brand reputation/image, Increase sales and thereby profit and Customers can access the shop in their locality.

REFERENCE

1. Alec Nicole Suarez, J. K. (2017). Impacts of Coffee Shop Business to Tourism Industry in Three Cities of Batangas, Philippines. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 14.
2. Aries Susanty, E. K. (2015, June). The Relationship between Brand Equity, Customer Satisfaction, and Brand Loyalty on Coffee Shop: Study of Excelso and Starbucks. *ASEAN MARKETING JOURNAL*, 7, 14-27.
3. Ashis Mishra, R. V. (2019). Retail shopper empowerment: A consumer-centric measure for store performance. *IIMB Management Review*, 31, 20-36. DOI:10.1016/j.iimb.2018.08.006
4. Brian Chiputwa, D. M. (2015). Food Standards, Certification, and Poverty among Coffee Farmers in Uganda. 66, 400-412. DOI:10.1016/j.worlddev.2014.09.006
5. Budi Rahardjo, R. H. (2019, June). Coffee Shop Business Model Analysis. *Integrated Journal of Business and Economics*, 3, 140-152. DOI:10.33019/ijbe.v3i2.153
6. Do Tu, L. (2017, May). Business plan-a a Vietnamese Coffee Shop in Helsinki.
7. Emanuel de Bellis, G. V. (2020). Autonomous Shopping Systems: Identifying and Overcoming Barriers to Consumer Adoption. 96, 74-87. DOI:10.1016/j.jretai.2019.12.004
8. Georgios Pardalis, B. M. (2019). One-stop-shop as an innovation, and construction SMEs: A Swedish perspective. *Energy Procedia*, 158, 2737-2743. DOI:10.1016/j.egypro.2019.02.031
9. Guillen-Royo, M. (2019). Sustainable consumption and wellbeing: Does on-line shopping matter? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 229, 1112-1124. DOI:10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.061
10. Hannu Vanharanta, J. K. (2015). Customers' conscious experience in a coffee shop. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 3, 618-625.
11. Hermawan, F. (2019, April). Designing a Strategic Business Plan and Financial Analysis-a case study of AHS GAN SHOP. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Researches*, 6. Retrieved from www.ijcar.net
12. Hung, L.-M. (2012). A Study of Consuming Behaviors of Budget Coffee. *Business and Management Research*, 1. DOI:10.5430/bmr.v1n1p48

13. Jr, L. F. (2013, August). Status of Coffee Shop Business in Batangas City: Basis for Business Operation Initiatives. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3. DOI:10.6007/IJARBS/v3-i8/156
14. Junio Andreti, N. H. (2013). The Analysis of Product, Price, Place, Promotion, and Service Quality on Customers' Buying Decision of Convenience Store: A Survey of Young Adults in Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*, 2(6), 72-78. Retrieved from www.managementjournal.info
15. M.Hemalatha, P. V. (2008, July). Multiattribute Analysis of the Retail Store Location Decision. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Management*.
16. Nadányiová, M. (2015). The Quality Mark SK and Its Impact on The Shopping Behavior of Slovak Consumers. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23. DOI:10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00467-0
17. Naiara Barbosa Carvalho, V. P. (2015, October). A discriminant function for validation of the cluster analysis and behavioral prediction of the coffee market. *Food Research International*, 77, 400-407. DOI:10.1016/j.foodres.2015.10.013
18. Porter, L. (2018). *Business Plan: The Coffee Project*. 5. Retrieved from <http://scholarworks.uark.edu/acctuht/29>
19. Qin, L. (2004). Strategic Analysis of best coffee in China.
20. Ringo, L. G. (2009). Utilizing GIS-Based Site Selection Analysis for Potential Customer Segmentation and. 11. Retrieved from <http://www.gis.smumn.edu>
21. S, D. D. (2016, September). APPLICATION OF GARRET RANKING TECHNIQUE: A PRACTICAL APPROACH. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 6(3).
22. Sadeeq Garba Abubakar, B. A. (2015, December). Achieving a sustainable competitive advantage and market growth through marketing strategy: A case example of a small family coffee shop. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 1(3).
23. Titik Sumarti, S. F. (2016). The Role and Position of Young Coffee Farmers: The Gap between Generations in the Coffee Business. *International Conference on Food, Agriculture and Natural Resources*, 6 500 - 509. DOI:10.1016/j.aaspro.2016.02.169
24. Wang, M. (2020). Research on Financial Analysis of Luckin Coffee. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 116, 25-29. Retrieved from <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>
25. Washburn, A. M. (2006, July). Observations at a Coffee Shop, Gleanings From a Think Tank. *Journal of Transformative Education*, 4, 195-201. DOI:10.1177/1541344606291638
26. Wen-Ko Liang, R.-A. W. (2012). Analysis of Coffee shop market—a Case study of UK.